

BEYOND "TRANSLATION OF A TRANSLATION": AUTHORIAL REWRITING AND INDIRECTNESS IN YAN GELING'S JINLING SHISAN CHAI

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The common definition of indirect translation as the "translation of a translation," while operationally useful, risks overlooking other forms of indirectness that may emerge prior to translation itself. Drawing on socio-narrative theory (Baker 2006), this paper examines Yan Geling's *Jinling Shisan Chai*, a story about women's sacrifice in the Nanjing Massacre, and its English translation *The Flowers of War*, to reveal how authorial reframing functions as a form of pre-translational mediation that produces effects analogous to indirect translation. The original novella, published in 2006, was subsequently rewritten and expanded into a longer Chinese version in 2011 for international circulation, which was then translated into English in 2012. Although the English version is technically a direct translation, the source text it translates is already a culturally and ideologically reconfigured version of the original.

The expanded Chinese version introduces documentary references concerning massacre victims and the search for surviving comfort women, foregrounding individual narratives of suffering and lived experiences. It enables comfort women to reclaim their trauma and voices, masking a decisive break with China's nationalist narrative that frames the Massacre primarily as a consumable testimony of Japanese atrocities serving national unity and victimhood. Meanwhile, this also challenges Japanese revisionist discourses that seek to deny or falsify wartime crimes. This narrative repositioning contributes to the later English version that meets Anglophone expectations of individualism and humanism. By analysing such repositioning, the paper proposes the notion of narrative and discursive indirectness to complement language-based models of indirect translation. It stresses how mediation can occur through authorial narrative reframing and cultural anticipation, thereby creating a "two-arched bridge" in which translation operates on an already mediated source. It challenges rigid distinctions between direct and indirect translation and suggests that indirectness should be understood as a spectrum shaped by power, discursive orientation, and global literary circulation.

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